

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

D6.8: Practice abstracts part 2 – before the second review meeting

WP6– Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

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Document Information

Grant Agreement	771738	Acronym	NextFOOD	
Full Project Title	Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system			
Start Date	01/05/2018	Duration	48	
Project URL	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/			
Deliverable	D6.8: Practice abstracts part 2 – before the second review meeting			
Working Package	WP6 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	30/04/2021	Actual	29/04/2021
Nature	R	Dissemination Level	P	
WP Leader	AFS – American Farm School, Greece			
Authors	Line Lindner, Katherine Flynn (ISEKI-Food Association, Austria)			
Contributors	AFS, University of Chile, SLU All partners			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	16/04/2021	Draft	Review	SLU, AFS
1.0	29/04/2021	Final	Review	SLU, AFS

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Executive summary

Deliverable 6.8 contains the second set of Practice Abstracts to feed into to the website of the European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) for broad dissemination to practitioners - farmers, farmers' groups, advisors, researchers and all other stakeholders of the agrifood and forestry systems in a concise and easily understandable way.

Practice Abstracts (PAs) follow a common dissemination format containing a short summary which describes the main information/recommendations/practice that can serve the end-users in their daily practice.

In total 100 Practice Abstracts will be collected and submitted during the duration of NextFood and they will all feed into the EIP-AGRI website and be part of deliverables D6.7, D6.8 and D6.9.

19 Practice abstracts were included in D6.7. In D6.8, 42 practice are included and the remaining 39 practice abstracts will be included in D6.9.

All practice abstracts contained in D6.8 were subject to a review process in which the reviewers (ISEKI-Food Association) are 1) holding individual online meetings with the authors to identify topic(s) and set a deadline; 2) authors write the abstracts; 3) reviewers review the abstracts and return to authors for verification; and 4) the practice abstracts are published on the [EIP-Agri website](#), on the [NextFood website](#); disseminated on NextFood's social media channels ([Facebook](#), [Instagram](#), [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#)); and a selection is included both in the NextFood internal and external [newsletters](#). Furthermore, NextFood Partner University of Chile is in the process of translating the practice abstracts into Spanish.

Innovative Online Learning: A Team Competition

Nextfood Practice Abstract #20	Partner	ISEKI-Food Association, Austria Katherine Flynn
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Short title in English	Innovative Online Learning: A Team Competition
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>In the FoodFactory-4-Us Student Competition Games, Master students in food-related programmes develop and present a unique solution to a real-life food industry challenge. Self-organised teams of 3 to 5 students respond to a widely publicised call with a short description of their team and solution. An Advisory Board of academia and industry choose the top 10 teams to participate in the 4-month competition. Team members attend 6 online trainings: a practice presentation, virtual visit, mentoring workshop, soft skills and 2 typical expert topic presentations - but with topics chosen by the students. The competition ends at a Virtual Conference where teams present their solutions and the winner is announced. Industry- and Association-sponsored prizes include cash and a guaranteed presentation slot at an upcoming professional conference.</p> <p>An online competition can be an action learning environment. This requires a lot of planning and attention to detail. We use 2 instructors to run the competition - from preparing the call for applications, to answering student emails, to uploading information to the competition website, to running the online trainings. Instructions on the website and in slides shown during online trainings must be crystal clear, easy to understand and to find. Students go back many times to check exactly what is expected of them, including the evaluation criteria. We included teamwork as part of the evaluation and were careful to explain teamwork expectations and exactly how we measure teamwork. Finally, regular and personal contact with all students is essential for a sense of community.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa20.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Involving local actors in action research

Nextfood Practice Abstract #21	Partner CIHEAM, Italy Suzana Madzaric and Virginia Belsanti
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Short title in English	Involving local actors in action research
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Engagement of local actors and creation of linkages with local agri-food systems is a successful element in the action research approach developed in the MSc course in Organic Agriculture (MOA) by the CIHEAM team. Learners are confronted with sustainability issues affecting decisions of local actors and are involved in working out concrete solutions together with them. This ensures an active role of local actors that become key informants and participants in the problem-solving and learning process. CIHEAM engaged the LAG (Local Action Group) as key stakeholders in the Alto Salento region. Together with local actors, MOA students were mobilised by the LAG, focusing on initiatives to promote typical products of the region. At the end of the process, learners and local actors delivered workable proposals to have access to LAG funding, thereby achieving a shared vision for medium-term attainable results.</p> <p>It is recommended to involve a local authority like LAG that has ties with the region and can mobilise a range of local actors; local actors should represent different perspectives (environmental, social, economic, cultural) and reflect different interests in the agri-food system; learners should be engaged in activities supporting concrete initiatives aimed at local sustainable development (action plans, funding applications, etc.); participation and dialogue should receive due space to build networks and linkages with local actors; visits and meetings (also remotely) have to be planned in accordance with the class activities; the local authority should be an active part of the process while motivation should be based on common interest achievement but also on financial reward for the time and effort devoted.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa21.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Farmers as teachers of Agroecology

Nextfood Practice Abstract #22	Partner	University of Calcutta, Welthungerhilfe, India Ritam Bhattacharya, Anshuman Das, Parthiba Basu,
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Short title in English	Farmers as teachers of Agroecology
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>During the 3-month certificate course in Agroecology at the University of Calcutta, target students act as farmer trainers and extension workers. The backbone of the course is for students to understand the social, economic and ecological challenges faced by smallholder farmers and looking for options to address those challenges. The students engage in multiple forms of interaction with the farmers. At the beginning, students are staying at farms which are well-established zero external input integrated farms to learn from farmers about planning, techniques, practices, interaction with the market etc. Interaction is free flowing but also structured in the sense that farmers are already oriented to making the students work on the farm, explain about farm planning, resource flow etc.</p> <p>A few weeks into the course, students are again staying with the farmers to assess the challenges through various Participatory Resource Appraisal (PRA) tools.</p> <p>And at the end, students are again sent to the same farmers to test solutions together. Farmers give their feedback about students' performance as to their eagerness to learn, inhibitions in staying and working on the farms, and as regards engagement.</p> <p>Main practical recommendations</p> <p>Acting as farmer trainers and extension workers, students learn that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • farmers communicate and express themselves differently than the way in which they may be used to; • observation is key to ask questions to farmers. • it is good to plan the day together with the farmers. • it is important to stay and have food with the farmer's family. • keeping a student's diary about the farm work is helpful. • it is important for each of the students to summarize the everyday learning and present it to the larger group of students.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa22.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

FARM VISIT: How to open your farm to the students

Nextfood Practice Abstract #23	Partner	UNISG, Italy Paola Migliorini and Natalia Rastorgueva
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Short title in English	FARM VISIT: How to open your farm to the students
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Didactic farm visits organised by UNISG have mutual benefits as for the students as for the farmers, and include constructive dialogue and knowledge sharing between students and farmers, practical experience, networking and building new relations. During well-organised farm visits, the farmers have a good opportunity to engage young people into farming activity (sometimes the students have several hands-on activities on farm), to promote his products, and to provide practical cases for learning.</p> <p>Main Practical Recommendations: The farmer should be able to introduce his/her farm and all related activities to a group of the students. This kind of activity requires farmer's knowledge in several fields such as Agronomy, Ecology, Natural Sciences, Food Technology and so on, as well as appropriate language skills. But even more important is the motivation and the passion for this kind of work and agriculture. In fact, the first point to share with visitors is: why am I farming? What does it mean for me? What is my philosophy of farming?</p> <p>In order to offer a good and efficient farm visits a good organisation is needed: time management, subdivision of the farm activities, a well-prepared walk into the farm. Also good organisation of farm visits should take in account seasonal differences in farm activity.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa23.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Focus group interviews: What do practitioners and stakeholders say about future needed skills in a sustainable food system?

Nextfood Practice Abstract #24	Partner RUC, Denmark Stine Rosenlund Hansen,
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Short title in English	Focus group interviews: What do practitioners and stakeholders say about future needed skills in a sustainable food system?
Short title in native language	Fokusgruppe interviews: Hvad siger praktikere og interessenter om behovet for fremtidige færdigheder i et bæredygtigt fødevarer-system?
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	With the purpose of gaining insight into different views on which skills will be needed to support a sustainable transition in the agrifood system, 20 focus group interviews have been completed in 9 different countries (Europe, Chile, India, Ethiopia). They represent a broad range of actors, including farmers and advisors, actors within fisheries and fish farms, food enterprises, researchers/teachers, students, ministerial bodies, and NGOs. The focus groups generally pointed out that a sustainable transition in the agrifood system is characterized by complexity and continuous change. Therefore, all involved actors need to have the skills to keep adapting to new challenges and possibilities, but also to push such development through skills in life-long learning, problem-solving and innovation. It is also highlighted that the complexity requires that solutions are developed across current divisions, such as those between the scientific and practical, and divisions by sector, institution, culture, geography or generation. Leading to a need for skills in working collaboratively and in understanding the agrifood system as a larger whole. Thus, in order to support a sustainable transition, educators should ensure that the identified skills are catered for in relevant educational offers. This includes a more holistic and synchronized re-design of the knowledge institutions to support interdisciplinary collaborations and holistic systems perspectives. Furthermore, practitioners within the area of agriculture or the associated bio-value chains, should maintain an open mind-set amongst themselves and their employees/colleagues, and seek lifelong learning through networks, projects and supplementary- and further training.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	Med formål om at opnå indsigt i hvilke færdigheder, der er behov for, for at støtte en bæredygtig omstilling i landbrug- og fødevarer-systemet, er der gennemført 20 fokusgruppe interviews i 9 forskellige lande (Europa, Chile, Indien, Etiopien). Interviewene repræsenterer en bred vifte af forskellige aktører, inkl. landmænd og rådgivere, fiskeri/dambrug, fødevarer virksomheder, forskere/undervisere, studerende, ministerier og

	<p>NGO'er. Fokusgrupperne peger generelt på, at en bæredygtig omstilling er karakteriseret ved kompleksitet og konstant forandring. Derfor er det nødvendigt at alle involverede aktører har færdigheder til konstant at tilpasse sig de nye udfordringer og muligheder der opstår, men også samtidig til at drive sådanne forandringer gennem færdigheder i livslang læring, problem løsning og innovation. Det fremhæves også at kompleksiteten kalder på løsninger, der udvikles på tværs af skel, såsom skel mellem det videnskabelige og praktiske, og skel skabt af sektorer, institutioner, kultur, geografi eller generationer. Dette fører til et behov for færdigheder i at samarbejde og i at forstå fødevarer systemet som en større helhed. For at understøtte en bæredygtig omstilling er det derfor nødvendigt at undervise sikre at de identificerede færdigheder trænes i de relevante uddannelses tilbud. Dette inkluderer en mere holistisk og synkroniseret re-design af vidensinstitutionerne for at understøtte tværvideenskabelige samarbejder og holistiske systemperspektiver. Desuden er det væsentligt at praktikere inden for landbrug og de associerede værdikæder bevarer et åbent mind-set blandt dem selv og deres ansatte/kolleger, og søger livslang læring gennem netværk, projekter og efter- og videreuddannelse.</p>
<p>Link</p>	<p>nextfood-pa24.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)</p>

Peer reviewed literature review: What are the identified needed skills and competencies for a sustainable transition in the agrifood and forestry system

Nextfood Practice Abstract #25	Partner RUC, Denmark Laura Brandt Sørensen
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Short title in English	Peer reviewed literature review: What are the identified needed skills and competencies for a sustainable transition in the agrifood and forestry system
Short title in native language	Litteraturstudie: Hvilke færdigheder og kompetencer er der behov for i en bæredygtig omlægning af fødevarsystemet
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>With the purpose of gaining insight into different views on which skills will be needed to support a sustainable transition in the agrifood and forestry system a review of peer reviewed articles was completed. A 3-step methodology was adopted in order to ensure a rigorous and repeatable method: generation of keywords, systematic search, and extraction of skills. Searches were carried out between December 2018 and April 2019 in five databases. 34 articles were selected representing primary producers (farming, fishing and forestry workers), agronomists, researchers, decision-makers and policy-makers within agriculture, forestry, aquaculture, and food system. The peer reviewed literature review showed that sustainability is not an easy concept to identify, however, there is a need to learn how to navigate in a world of constant change and wicked problems. The literature review points towards needed skills such as;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • skills in understanding complexities in agrifood systems, and in real life practices • skills within life-long learning, as an ongoing process of learning and adapting on both local and global levels • skills in knowledge integration, including both the capability to learn how to integrate local knowledge with scientific knowledge, and involve other knowledgeable producers and consumers in knowledge development • skills in building and maintaining networks in order to facilitate knowledge sharing and interdisciplinarity <p>Thus, in order for a sustainable transition to happen a more holistic re-design of the knowledge institutions is needed to support knowledge integration, lifelong learning and a holistic system thinking of the complexities in agrifood systems.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	Med det formål at opnå indsigt i hvilke færdigheder, der er behov for i en bæredygtig omstilling i landbrug- og fødevarsystemet er der gennemført et litteraturstudie. En 3-trins metode var anvendt: generering af keywords, systematisk litteratursøgning og ekstraktion af færdigheder og kompetencer fra litteraturen. Litteratursøgning blev udarbejdet mellem december 2018 og 2019 indenfor fem databaser. 34 artikler blev udvalgt og

	<p>repræsenterer aktører som primære producenter, agronomer, forskere og forskellige beslutningstagere inden for landbrug, fiskeri, skovbrug og fødevare system.</p> <p>Bæredygtighed er et komplekst begreb uden entydig definition, hvilket betyder, at der ikke er en entydig måde, at forstå færdigheder og kompetencer på. Alligevel er der et behov for, at lære at navigere i en verden under konstant forandring og komplekse problemstillinger. Litteraturstudiet peger på færdigheder og kompetencer indenfor;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forståelser for kompleksiteter i fødevare systemer • Livslang lærings: en kontinuerlig og vedvarende læring og tilpasning på et lokalt og globalt plan • Videns integrering: integrere lokal viden med videnskabelig forskning • Netværksskabelse og vedligeholdelse af netværk, som bidrager til vidensdeling mellem professioner og discipliner <p>For at opnå en bæredygtig udvikling i fødevaresystemet, peger litteraturstudiet ligeledes på en forandring som indbefatter udviklingen af en bredere funderet uddannelses, som fokuserer på et holistisk perspektiv på systemtænkning i forhold til komplekse problemstillinger i fødevaresystemet.</p>
Link	nextfood-pa25.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

The NextFood Toolbox - Tools for practitioners in action-learning activities

Nextfood Practice Abstract #26	Partner	NMBU, Norway Åsmund Lægneid Steiro an and Lutgart Lenaerts,
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Short title in English	The NextFood Toolbox - Tools for practitioners in action-learning activities
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>The NextFood Toolbox is intended to support teachers at any level of the education system who are eager to test various aspects of the Nextfood educational approach.</p> <p>The toolbox diagram is the initial interface of the toolbox where users can click on each of the competences to explore relevant material related to them. For each competence, there are both examples of how to train them and descriptions of what they mean. There are also instructional videos! Whether a course is week - long or spans several months, participating educators will find examples of teaching materials suited to train all the competences within the context of action learning.</p> <p>The toolbox will be continually updated with new content throughout the project, so feel free to explore the current version and stay tuned for future updates!</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa26.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Requirements to interact with farmers and non-university actors in a field-based course

Nextfood Practice Abstract #27	Partner	Kerala University, India Manju S. Nair and Anupama Augustine
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Short title in English	Requirements to interact with farmers and non-university actors in a field-based course
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>University of Kerala hosts a One-month Certificate Course on Agroecology and Action Research for students from multidisciplinary backgrounds which employs flexible curricula, field action and peer learning. This includes farmers and non-university actors as facilitators. Students spend about two weeks at a farm, and farmers guide their learning. Agroecology course 2019 had support from farmers and local self-government officials. This experience produced major recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan the process of inclusion: The action plan developed to include non-university actors in Course contained; • Visiting prospective fields/institutions as an extension activity and understanding the nature (of farms), structure (of institutions) and meeting major stakeholders. • Conducting workshop with selected stakeholders and explaining the nuances of the course and expected role of each participant. • Listening to apprehensions and communicating benefits to stakeholders. • Make instruction/communication multi-lingual: The norm regarding medium of instruction as English at the University was made flexible and the farmers were given freedom to choose their language during discussions. This boosted confidence of illiterate farmers. • Familiarizing farmers and other stakeholders with University systems: Organizing seminars/symposiums prior to conduction of course and honoring of farmers. This made attitudinal change in both students and teachers and earned recognition for farmer
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa27.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Participating in action learning courses with students from multidisciplinary backgrounds

Nextfood Practice Abstract #28	Partner	Kerala University, India Manju S. Nair and Anupama Augustine,
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Short title in English	Participating in action learning courses with students from multidisciplinary backgrounds
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>The Certificate Course on Agroecology: Action Research and Education is for post graduate students from diverse disciplines at the University of Kerala. In 2019, twelve students attended: two from Agriculture/Forestry, five from social sciences and five from natural sciences. The course employed an action learning curriculum and student experiences during the course provide major recommendations:</p> <p>Peer learning is effective when students are from multidisciplinary backgrounds. Peers understand conflicts of ideas and/or problem situations when they are from diverse disciplines and can suggest solutions they have already experienced. The varied opinions that arise in a group improve group member interest in new subjects and thus stimulates new learning arenas.</p> <p>Group activities: Individual Group Plenary (IGP) model discussions, field work, rich pictures, mind maps and peer evaluation can be done. Through group activities, background and learning style of each student can be understood and so, students learn to respect diverse viewpoints.</p> <p>Division of group work according to the knowledge, strength and weaknesses of the student in the group is a good way to learn from each other.</p> <p>Dialoguing: Developing the competence of dialoguing through practice sessions can refine the ability of students to communicate and socialise.</p> <p>In sum, abilities such as communication, cooperation and sense of interdisciplinary understanding and multidimensional thinking can improve learning. Above all, a change in attitude of students and ability to make situational improvements or synthesis of opinions is important.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa28.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Strengthening farm communities through education involvement

Nextfood Practice Abstract #29	Partner	NMBU, Norway Åsmund Læg Reid Steiro,
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Short title in English	Strengthening farm communities through education involvement
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Farm size increases across Europe, and simultaneously farming communities shrink. Large farms may be more challenging to manage in accordance with sustainable farming practices, and farm managers are often not in a position to hire employees to cover such a need. There is however a potential solution to this challenge. Research shows that strong farm communities, modern advisory services and access to information makes it easier for individual farmers to practice farming in accordance with guidelines for sustainable farming practices.</p> <p>In the Nextfood project, we aim to shrink the gap between research, education and farming. We know that by involving students in action-oriented, real-life projects throughout their studies, they become much better prepared for working in those same real-life environments after graduation. In our project we study processes where students collaborate with stakeholders in society (farmers, food processors, policy makers, etc.). Based on reports from those stakeholders, we see that these collaborations are also very beneficial to them. This is so, because the students bring new information in addition to facilitating establishment of stronger communities by hosting meetings and workshops. Based on our experiences, we encourage all stakeholders in agrifood and forestry systems to engage with students, academics and advisors as much as possible. By bringing the education back into the fields where the real action is, we can hopefully strengthen our vital farming communities!</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa29.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Action Based Learning in an on-line environment during pandemic lockdown

Nextfood Practice Abstract #30	Partner	American Farm School, Greece Georgia Zafeiriou & Elisavet Papadopoulou
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Short title in English	Action Based Learning in an on-line environment during pandemic lockdown
Short title in native language	Βιωματική μάθηση σε διαδικτυακό περιβάλλον (Συνθήκες καραντίνας COVID-19)
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Due to the international COVID-19 situation there was a great need for the American Farm School to shift their learning and advising activities online while maintaining the highest quality. The AFS team found different good practice guidelines useful for different groups.</p> <p>At an organizational level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Place emphasis on positive outcomes of this experience and new skills that are developing. • Offer ongoing digital skills and digital technology training and offer ongoing support. • Use already existing Learning Management Systems. • Continuously investigate new possibilities for long-term good practices . • Organize frequent team reflection meetings. <p>With educators/advisors/farmers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate the value of digital devices/methods and digital skills development • Allow for adjustment to online meetings by meeting online unofficially before the first work meetings. • Be versatile in methods of communication used. • Simplify the massive online world through the provision of clear instructions. • Aim for small group sizes. • Reconsider material, offer more independent study, and engage more personally during online sessions. On-line learning can be more draining than physical presence learning. • Implement learning by teaching techniques (e.g. student presentations). • Include group discussion/reflection after each session. • Work with student-generated case studies. • Ensure emotional engagement.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Κατά τη διάρκεια των συνθηκών καραντίνας λόγω του COVID-19, αντιμετωπίσαμε την ανάγκη να μεταφέρουμε όλες μας τις εκπαιδευτικές και συμβουλευτικές δραστηριότητες σε online περιβάλλον.</p> <p>Ταυτόχρονα έπρεπε να διασφαλίσουμε ότι η ποιότητα των υπηρεσιών μας παρέμενε ακέραιη.</p> <p>Η ομάδα της ΑΓΣ, διερεύνησε και εφάρμοσε ορισμένες οδηγίες καλών πρακτικών για διαδικτυακή μάθηση και επαγγελματική</p>

	<p>δραστηριότητα και κάποια από τα αποτελέσματα παραθέτονται παρακάτω:</p> <p>Σε επίπεδο Οργανισμού:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Δίνουμε έμφαση στα θετικά αποτελέσματα αυτής της εμπειρίας και στις δεξιότητες που αναπτύσσονται. • Βεβαιωθείτε ότι καλύπτετε τις ανάγκες εκπαίδευσης σε ψηφιακές δεξιότητες όλων των εμπλεκομένων. • Χρησιμοποιείτε ήδη υπάρχουσες πλατφόρμες διαχείρισης μαθησιακών διαδικασιών. • Διερευνάτε τις δυνατότητες που αναπτύσσονται και την πιθανότητα υιοθέτησης αυτών που αξίζουν σαν μόνιμη πρακτική. • Ενθαρρύνετε τις ομαδικές συναντήσεις της ομάδας σας. <p>Οι εκπαιδευτές και οι σύμβουλοί μας δούλεψαν με τις παρακάτω οδηγίες:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Τονίστε την χρησιμότητα των νέων τεχνολογιών και την ανάπτυξη ψηφιακών δεξιοτήτων. • Δώστε την ευκαιρία στους χρήστες/μαθητές να προσαρμοστούν κάνοντας κάποιες άτυπες συναντήσεις πριν χρειαστεί να κάνετε δουλειά. • Δείξτε προσαρμοστικότητα στα μέσα επικοινωνίας. • Δώστε πολύ ξεκάθαρες και απλές οδηγίες. • Όποτε είναι δυνατό δημιουργήστε μικρές ομάδες. • Ο χρόνος online είναι πολύ πιο κουραστικός από τον χρόνο φυσικής επαφής. Επαναπροσδιορίστε το υλικό σας και δώστε περισσότερο υλικό για ανεξάρτητη μελέτη. • Χρησιμοποιείτε τεχνικές μάθησης μέσω διδασκαλίας. • Συμπεριλάβετε χρόνο για ομαδική συζήτηση/ανατροφοδότηση σε κάθε μάθημα. • Δουλέψτε με μελέτες περίπτωσης που φέρνουν οι εκπαιδευόμενοι. • Σιγουρέψτε την συναισθηματική εμπλοκή των χρηστών.
<p>Link</p>	<p>nextfood-pa30.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)</p>

How to be a successful agroecology student (for students)

Nextfood Practice Abstract #31	Partner NMBU, Norway Lutgart Lenaerts
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Short title in English	How to be a successful agroecology student (for students)
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>To be(come) a successful agroecology student starts with a strong interest in the long-term sustainability of agrifood systems, an open mind, and eagerness to learn and act.</p> <p>Firstly, to learn about sustainability of agriculture and food systems, you should be keen on understanding and solving complex problems. Moreover, you should be eager to work on these problems in international teams. If you want to make a difference in agrifood systems by linking knowledge to action, you have already one of the most important qualities to become a successful agroecology student.</p> <p>Secondly, you should be open to multiple views and be (?) willing to learn individually and in groups (peer learning). Therefore, you should be(come) a good communicator and facilitator. Key to engaging in your own learning process is to train yourself in the competence of reflection. You should regularly take time to reflect. This will enrich your learning process and help you to become a life-long learner.</p> <p>Thirdly, you should be keen on phenomenon-based and action-oriented learning. Do you like to start learning by observing what happens in the world out there? Do you like to learn how to take action that contributes to long-term sustainability of agrifood systems? If the answer is yes, then you have the right mindset. To be a successful agroecology student means that you have all these interests, engage fully in your learning process, and enjoy the journey. Have fun!</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa31.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Integrating systems thinking into farmer courses

Nextfood Practice Abstract #32	Partner	University of Calcutta/Welthungerhilfe, India Ritam Bhattacharya, Anshuman Das, Parthiba Basu,
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Short title in English	Integrating systems thinking into farmer courses
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>The target students, in the 3-month certificate course in Agroecology at the University of Calcutta, are farmer trainers and extension workers. The backbone of the course is to understand the social, economical and ecological challenges faced by small holder farmers and looking for options to address those challenges.</p> <p>Facing the difficulty of a reductionist approach to resolve the various systemic challenges of food and farm systems, in the design of the course, we have tried to create a systems model for the concept of agroecology among farmers thereby integrating systems thinking into the course. We are exploring various key conceptual successions to explain the root of agroecology, clarifying the few conceptual areas of various spectrum of the agrifood system and highlighting the limitations of conventional agricultural farming and food system. The students are exposed to various accumulated and then synthesized aspects of agroecology. Finally, systems thinking is applied to develop a more comprehensive model of farm systems to promote the understanding and application of agroecology.</p> <p>Main practical recommendations for integrating systems thinking into farmer courses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The agri food system has a nested hierarchy. Each part of the system has on its own but when it meets with others it becomes part of the system. - Each system is interconnected to form a bigger suprasystem. - The environmental, social, and economic systems are closely linked, interacting and sometimes overlapping. - Integration of environmental, social and economic systems are important to improve the quality of life.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa32.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

How to include Gender in teaching agriculture and forestry

Nextfood Practice Abstract #33	Partner	Welthungerhilfe Nora Pistor
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Short title in English	How to include Gender in teaching agriculture and forestry
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>The gender dimension is visibly integrated in the teaching of agriculture and forestry-related subjects. This encompasses both the inclusion of the category of gender as teaching content and the institutional integration of gender as criterion of personnel equity.</p> <p>This is important as teaching contents often overlook important gender relations and thereby reproduce patriarchal systems existing in the fields of agriculture and forestry. Female students and staff, particularly in leadership positions, are often underrepresented in departments of agriculture and forestry education institutions. Equality and diversity of students and staff will create higher learning impacts and contribute to achieve the goals of equity and equality in society.</p> <p>Main Practical Recommendations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create a Gender Working Group in the department to develop a plan for integrating gender in teaching. 2. Identify gender gaps and opportunities for gender integration in teaching curricula. 3. Develop a plan to integrate gender into teaching curricula based on assessment findings. Ensure top-level buy-in and support for implementing the plan. Define the purpose(s) of this activity, e.g. to increase ratio of female students in these faculties, or support gender-specific research. 4. Raise awareness among staff and train teaching staff on gender through professional gender trainers. 5. Offer courses of varying levels on gender (from introductory to advanced) for various topics in agriculture/ forestry to students. 6. Formally integrate gender as a teaching category in the curricula of agriculture and forestry faculties.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa33.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Challenges in training Reflection: Facilitator perspective of working with high school students

Nextfood Practice Abstract #34	Partner	University of Oradea, Romania Anamaria Supuran & Adrian Timar,
Short title in English	Challenges in training Reflection: Facilitator perspective of working with high school students	
Short title in native language		
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>As part of the practice-oriented course in food innovation at the University of Oradea in Romania, facilitators practice the NextFood core competences with university and vocational high school students. Due to age difference and knowledge level of the two student categories, a series of challenges were brought to facilitators' attention when training the competence reflection. As part of the NextFood action-learning process, students write a "learner reflection document" in which they link experience, theory and personal reflections as regards the contents and processes of the course, the learning itself and the implications for further individual development. Particularly for high school students, it was a complex process to write the document at the level of thinking and of transposing the thinking into words. Facilitators spent additional time providing guidance and giving examples, keywords, expressions and sentences to high school students and noted that university students were able to start writing their documents immediately after the end of each course meeting. Furthermore, facilitators observed, during reflection sessions, that high school students had difficulties expressing their thoughts and feelings verbally being shy towards their older team colleagues. Facilitators intervened when necessary by supporting them with additional questions or advice. In the end, the participation level of the high school students increased with each meeting, so that in the second part of the course there was no difference among the team members. We may conclude that despite challenges due to age and background, using patience and additional effort led to the levelling of discrepancies and eventually to their disappearance.</p>	
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes		
Link	nextfood-pa34.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)	

Finding solutions to learners' acquisition of hands-on experience during the pandemic

Nextfood Practice Abstract #35	Partner	University of Oradea, Romania Anamaria Supuran & Adrian Timar
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Short title in English	Finding solutions to learners' acquisition of hands-on experience during the pandemic
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>At the University of Oradea, Romania, in the interdisciplinary course "Students and farmers taking food innovations from idea to market", learners work in teams on product development thereby training competences and skills ranging from technical, soft, to entrepreneurial and ICT skills. In dedicated reflection sessions, learners are made aware of connections that are normally established in real life during product development within the research teams performing cooperative learning working together on specific projects.</p> <p>Following the pandemic hitting Europe in the spring of 2020, however, communication was disrupted among team members and among and with facilitators, teachers and other actors involved in the course. Thus, communication was transferred to the digital environment. The lack of real life experiences in the product development process was also significant as learners could not acquire hands-on knowledge and skills related to the technology, products and operation of machinery. Thus, real life experiences were replaced with videos supporting the learning process. Furthermore, due to the limited amount of learners present during course meetings, brainstorming sessions and learner arenas - usually providing space for presenting and debating research results in a very specific and focused way and leading to self-reflection and collective reflection - were no longer available in a face-to-face format. It took time until facilitators found solutions to create space for online conferences, workshops and reflection sessions in the digital arena. This process came to place through listening and learning from other partners' experiences in the peer learning working groups supporting the NextFood cases.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	nextfood-pa35.pdf (nextfood-project.eu)

Chat app as a tool for reflection, dialogue, and observation with forestry professionals

Nextfood Practice Abstract #36	Partner Skogforsk, Sweden Line Djupström and Lotta Woxblom
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Short title in English	Chat app as a tool for reflection, dialogue, and observation with forestry professionals
Short title in native language	Chatt APP som verktyg för reflektion, dialog och observation
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Skogforsk is running a vocational course for forestry professionals aiming at a higher understanding about logging techniques, strategies, and methods to increase quality and number of microhabitats in production forests.</p> <p>An important step in the learning process and to achieve deep learning is to inspire and create prerequisite for reflection. Working with professionals is quite different from the situation of working with students. Professional machine operators do not have scheduled time to work with projects and written assignments, like full-time students have.</p> <p>Instead, reflection can take place at case-meetings, in a good dialogue, and between meetings where knowledge is tested in practice. For this purpose, we use an app (Supertext) where researchers and forestry professionals, on equal terms, create posts from everyday work or observations linked to the theme of the previous case-meeting. Posts can be questions fostering a (short) dialogue and further knowledge transfer or observations acting as proof of an increased understanding and knowledge of the subject.</p> <p>As an example: a machine operator posted a picture of how high-cut stumps were used to mark an area with substrates important for biological diversity. Researchers then responded and confirmed the action and asked if it caused a major deviation from the original plan for felling.</p> <p>Conclusions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a platform that enables reflection between case-meetings • The platform should give participants the possibility to participate on equal terms • Appoint a responsible who keeps the dialogue alive and encourages input
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Skogforsk driver ett projekt som syftar till en högre förståelse för avverknings tekniker, strategier och metoder för att öka kvaliteten och antalet mikrohabitat i produktions skogar. Vårt projekt bedrivs som en yrkeskurs för skogsbrukare. Ett viktigt steg i lärandeprocessen och för att uppnå djupinläring är att inspirera och skapa förutsättningar för reflektion. Att arbeta med yrkesverksamma skiljer sig mycket från situationen att arbeta med studenter. Professionella maskinoperatörer har inte, som</p>

	<p>heltidsstudenter, schemalagd tid att arbeta med projekt och skriftliga uppgifter. I stället kan reflektion ske vid ett projektmöte, i en bra dialog, men för att skapa mervärde av mötet krävs en pågående reflektion och att kunskapen testas i praktiken. Mellan projektsammankomsterna använde vi en APP (Supertext) där forskare och praktiker inom skogsbruket, på lika villkor, skapade inlägg från vardagliga händelser eller observation som kopplade till temat för tidigare projektsammankomst. Ibland var inläggen en fråga vilket då skapade en (kort) dialog och ytterligare kunskapsöverföring. Andra gånger var inläggen en observation som fungerade som ett kvitto på en ökad förståelsen och kunskap kring ämnet. Som ett exempel: en praktiker gjorde ett inlägg i form av en bild på hur man använt kulturstubbar för att markera en plats med substrat viktiga för biologisk mångfald. Ett kvitto på att man reflekterat över vad vi pratat om och hittar lösningar för att skapa bättre förutsättningar för ett hållbart skogsbruk. Forskarna bekräftade aktiviteten och frågade om det krävdes stora avvikelser från den planerade avverkningen.</p>
<p>Link</p>	<p>Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)</p>

How to use time efficiently in action-learning courses

Nextfood Practice Abstract #37	Partner	American Farm School, Greece Elisavet Papadopoulou and Georgia Zafeiriou
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Short title in English	How to use time efficiently in action-learning courses
Short title in native language	Καλή διαχείριση χρόνου στη βιωματική μάθηση.
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>In action- learning, besides knowledge content, it is essential that facilitators allocate time efficiently for learners to develop a close relationship with the subject matter and their teammates; communication and other interpersonal skills; and to deal with difficulties and learn from mistakes. To that end, it is recommended that facilitators:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure that students possess the necessary specific knowledge required. 2. Allocate time generously for action-learning techniques and allow students to develop their experience with minimal intervention. Intervene only if students are going in an unwanted direction or need help. 3. Make sure that students know how much time they have for a given tasks. 4. Give time warnings when activities come close to an end. 5. Take notes on how much time an activity has taken and the point that the activity has reached. This will help you with future activity planning. 6. Aim for smaller groups. 7. Allow time for student reflection at the end of each action-learning activity. Much of the learning will happen during reflection. 8. Be aware that each group has its own dynamics and that they may be distracted due to the “free” setting. Try to keep such distractions in mind and redirect attention to the subject matter. 9. Be clear about the outcomes you are expecting from each activity. When appropriate, share these expectations with the parties involved. 10. Are aware that action- learning can be either top-bottom or bottom-up meaning that students are either given the context of the experience (experience to knowledge) or they are practicing knowledge that they already have (knowledge to experience). The first takes much more time and needs more time for reflection.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Στα βιωματικά μαθήματα υπάρχουν πράγματα που είναι πιο σημαντικά από το γνωστικό περιεχόμενο, όπως η ανάπτυξη σχέσεων με το αντικείμενο και τα μέλη της ομάδας, η ανάπτυξη επικοινωνίας και διαπροσωπικών δεξιοτήτων, ευκαιρίες αντιμετώπισης δυσκολιών και ευκαιρίες όπου μπορεί κανείς να κάνει λάθη.</p> <p>Γι' αυτό, χρειάζεται να αφιερώσουμε αποκλειστικό χρόνο για βιωματική μάθηση και να μην φορτώνουμε τον χρόνο αυτό με καινούριο γνωστικό υλικό.</p>

	<p>1) Σιγουρευτείτε ότι οι μαθητές σας έχουν ήδη τη γνώση που χρειάζονται πριν το μάθημα.</p> <p>2) Διαθέστε γενναιόδωρα χρόνο για βιωματικές τεχνικές στην διάρκεια των οποίων επεμβαίνετε όσο το δυνατό λιγότερο. Αφήστε τους μαθητές σας να ζήσουν την εμπειρία κι επέμβετε μόνο αν κάνουν σοβαρά λάθη ή χρειάζονται βοήθεια.</p> <p>3) Σιγουρευτείτε ότι οι μαθητές ξέρουν πόσο χρόνο έχουν για την κάθε δραστηριότητα.</p> <p>4) Δώστε προειδοποιήσεις για τέλος χρόνου.</p> <p>5) Σημειώστε πόσο χρόνο παίρνει η κάθε δραστηριότητα και σε πιο σημείο φτάσατε για μελλοντικό προγραμματισμό.</p> <p>6) Κάντε μικρότερες ομάδες.</p> <p>7) Δώστε χρόνο για ανατροφοδότηση και αναστοχασμό στο τέλος του μαθήματος. Είναι διαδικασία σημαντική για τη μάθηση.</p> <p>8) Κάθε ομάδα έχει δική της δυναμική και πιθανά προβλήματα. Η βιωματική μάθηση είναι πιο «ελεύθερη» και οι πιθανότητες για απόσπαση της προσοχής μεγαλύτερες. Προβλέψτε τυχόν διασπάσεις και καθοδηγήστε την προσοχή πίσω στο θέμα όταν χρειάζεται.</p> <p>9) Να σαφείς προσδοκίες από κάθε δραστηριότητα. Όπου πρέπει, μοιραστείτε τις προσδοκίες σας.</p> <p>10) Στη βιωματική μάθηση υπάρχουν δυο εκδοχές. Είτε θέλετε να αποκτήσουν οι μαθητές σας μια εμπειρία στην οποία θα θέσετε τα πλαίσια μετά ή έχετε θέσει τα πλαίσια και θέλετε να αποκτήσουν πρακτική εμπειρία. Η πρώτη περίπτωση απαιτεί πολύ περισσότερο χρόνο για ανατροφοδότηση και αναστοχασμό. Να είστε σίγουροι για το τι θέλετε να καταφέρετε και πώς θα το κάνετε.</p>
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

How to encourage faculty to use action-learning activities

Nextfood Practice Abstract #38	Partner	American Farm School, Greece Elisavet Papadopoulou and Georgia Zafeiriou
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Short title in English	How to encourage faculty to use action-learning activities
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Designing action-learning courses requires effort; a different set of skills and attitudes; and at times a shift in mindset from the part of academic faculty. This is often challenging as it requires more flexibility and creativity than mainstream teaching methodologies. For the educational organization, it is important to make a conscious decision towards shifting to action-learning which in turn requires that faculty is motivated to integrate action-learning in their educational activities and a structured support system encouraging and rewarding their efforts. In turn, faculty may develop closer and more satisfying relationships with their students, better learning outcomes, higher job satisfaction and good status among peers. Below a list of actions that an organization can adopt in order to enhance action-learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Make use of good examples. Allow students and faculty using action-learning methods to disseminate and even display their work and projects. Social capital is a powerful drive and motive. •Ask students for their opinion about the course and follow up on the results. This is extremely important because it shows consistency and gives value to student learning experience. •Create a mindset of development and support instead of criticism among faculty. When professors need to improve their teaching methodologies, they should be able to find suitable resources and support. •Create a newsletter or other publication tools that are dedicated to teaching methodologies. •Organize workshops dedicated to action-learning methodologies. •Allow for organizational and budget flexibility encouraging the involvement of market actors to visit your organization, field trips and extra curriculum seminars and workshops.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Gaps analysis in research and education of agri-food and forestry sectors

Nextfood Practice Abstract #39	Partner CIHEAM, Italy Suzana Madzaric and Virginia Belsanti
Short title in English	Gaps analysis in research and education of agri-food and forestry sectors
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>To respond to the needs of the agri-food and forestry sector, education and research is required to adapt and update their curricula so that any gaps in providing the necessary skills are filled. To steer current and new educational programmes and research agendas in line with the sector's needs NextFood conducted a skill gap analysis within the project consortium based on data provided by 21 partner institutions' course programmes (education) and results of an online survey distributed among the project partners (research).</p> <p>Educational programmes were analysed in terms of catering for different categories of skills considered crucial for the sectors of interest. This was guided by a skill inventory carried out in a different project activities and fed by multiple relevant sources (NextFood D1.1). Results revealed that learning methodologies are mostly relying on traditional class lectures, while action and experiential learning tools, although currently adopted, are still lagging. Delivery of technical skills prevails over soft skills, i.e. collaborative, system thinking, change management, etc.</p> <p>Research gaps were assessed through a survey including both closed and open questions and focused on the identification of current gaps especially concerning alignment between sector needs and educational/research offer.</p> <p>Recommendation: stronger focus should be placed on participatory and multi- and inter-disciplinary research, while in terms of thematic areas a stronger role should be given to research on social aspects. To close the current gaps, a multi-stakeholder steady dialogue should be ensured and results should inform the design of educational programmes and research agendas to effectively respond to the sector's needs.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Supporting reflection: use of “learning memories and key messaging”

Nextfood Practice Abstract #40	Partner CIHEAM, Italy Suzana Madzaric and Virginia Belsanti
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Short title in English	Supporting reflection: use of “learning memories and key messaging”
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Reflection needs encouragement through targeted support that can drive students to combine theory with experiences and evolve into a competence. Alternative learning sources contribute to this purpose. By adopting the use of “Learning memories” and “Key messages” students developed the competences of participation, observation and dialogue- through establishing linkages between theory, field experiences and interaction with stakeholders.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning memories: field visit experiences were linked with knowledge acquired from scientific articles by using a simple guideline where each experience-visit, meeting, group discussion- had to be related to literature evidence, reflected upon and then reported highlighting what was learned and would like to learn more. • Key messages: this task helped to summarise what was learned in the interactions with stakeholders into key concepts to be used in the development of the group project. It mainly concerned visits to actors not directly related to the case studies where students were asked to listen and observe while looking at the details and how certain mechanisms, concepts and experiences coming from different contexts could support their activities. <p>Recommendations: While students at the beginning of the course were not fully aware of the importance of reflecting on every step of their activities, neither in written nor in oral form, as they fulfilled the above tasks, comprehension of the value of reflection started to kick in as they realised that they had produced a “valuable repository” consisting of all the information they had collected and developed which they could use for their final reporting.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Students' development of reflection and discussion combining individual and group work

Nextfood Practice Abstract #41	Partner CIHEAM, Italy Suzana Madzaric and Virginia Belsanti
Short title in English	Students' development of reflection and discussion combining individual and group work
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Learning based on theory and experience is what develop competences after a process of reflection that establishes the bond between the two. This moment of reflection can happen individually or in group work. In the MSc course in Organic Agriculture (MOA) organised by CIHEAM, Italy, we have asked students to use what they have learned in the classroom to develop guidelines for interviewing actors they have chosen for their project and analyse the role of social capital development in agriculture in each specific context. Those guidelines had to be developed in groups discussing priorities, context specificities and objectives This process ended with the finalisation of a check list (guide for an interview). Students reflected on the results individually and documented this in a short report. In parallel, they had to discuss those results in the group and combine all the findings in a logic and consistent way to allow them to prepare a group presentation illustrating their individual experience and highlighting common findings. This triggered further discussion among all the groups and provided ground for further development in the following assignments and final project presentations.</p> <p>Recommendations: It is very important to structure clearly each step of the individual and group tasks in order to avoid confusion and provide a rational schedule that facilitates the understanding of the process and comprehension of the common objective as well as the individual one.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Playing games on serious stuff

Nextfood Practice Abstract #42	Partner University of Oradea, Romania Anamaria Supuran
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Short title in English	Playing games on serious stuff
Short title in native language	Joaca cu lucruri serioase
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Within the practice-oriented course in food innovation at the University of Oradea in Romania, students are designing six innovative food products. One activity undertaken when finding packaging solutions needed for the six food products is playing the serious game Simplycycle. The game helps students asking the right questions, think critically and analyse certain types of packaging and find solutions for dangerous materials. The game does not promote competition among students but encourages collaboration and communication within the team. It also stimulates creativity and visionary thinking. The game consists of a table board, two sets of cards and a pawn placed at the start position in the red area. One set of cards includes examples of packaging and information of the materials (their level of danger being marked with: red=very dangerous, green=safe). The groups are asked to replace the dangerous ingredients/materials of the respective packaging with others that are safe for the environment. Students need to collaborate to find the best solution. Finally, the facilitator decides if the team can move its pawn forward on the board in case the solution is acceptable. In the case there is no solution, the group is asked to read the suggestion given by the game but the pawn cannot be moved. The final objective of the game is for the group to succeed in moving the pawn from the red to the green area on the table board with each good solution delivered.</p> <p>Because the game is not designed to consider only packaging solutions, teachers designed their own cards serving better the purpose of the course. By playing Simplycycle, students succeeded in finding innovative solutions for the raised problems and the level of involvement and participation was very high.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Cursul organizat de Universitatea din Oradea are în vedere dezvoltarea a șase produse alimentare inovatoare. Una din activitățile realizate în cadrul discuțiilor despre ambalajele aferente celor 6 produse a fost utilizarea jocului serios Simplycycle.</p> <p>Jocul constă într-o tablă de joc, două seturi de cărți și un pion plasat pe poziția de start în zona roșie. Un set de cărți include exemple de ambalaje și informații despre materialele pe care le conțin (nivelul de pericol fiind marcat cu: roșu = foarte periculos, verde = sigur).</p> <p>Studentii au fost rugați să înlocuiască materialele periculoase ale ambalajului respectiv cu altele sigure pentru mediu. Studenții au trebuit să colaboreze pentru a găsi cea mai bună soluție. În cele din urmă, facilitatorul a decis dacă pionul poate înainta pe tablă,</p>

	<p>În cazul în care soluția a fost fezabilă. În caz contrar, grupul a fost rugat să citească sugestia dată de joc, dar în acest caz pionul nu a putut fi mutat. Obiectivul final al jocului a fost ca grupul să reușească să mute pionul din zona roșie în cea verde, fiecare mutare însemnând o soluție bună furnizată de grup.</p> <p>Deoarece jocul nu a fost conceput să ia în considerare doar ambalajele, profesorii și-au conceput propriile cărți de joc care au servit mai bine scopului cursului.</p> <p>Jucând Simplycycle, studenții au reușit să găsească soluții inovatoare pentru problemele ridicate, iar nivelul de implicare și participare a fost foarte ridicat.</p> <p>Jocul îi ajută pe jucători să pună întrebările corecte, să analizeze critic anumite ambalaje și să găsească soluții pentru materialele periculoase pe care acestea le conțin. Jocul nu promovează competiția dintre jucători, ci încurajează colaborarea și dialogul în cadrul echipei. De asemenea, stimulează creativitatea și gândirea vizionară.</p>
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Oscar food awards

Nextfood Practice Abstract #43	Partner	University of Oradea, Romania Anamaria Supuran
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Short title in English	Oscar food awards
Short title in native language	Decernarea premiilor Oscar
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>One of the most appreciated activities during the course in “Students and farmers taking food innovations from idea to market”, run by the University of Oradea, Romania, is the organization of sensory analysis of several food products that students have designed or brought into the laboratory. These activities are followed by an Oscar awarding contest giving prizes for: Oscar for the most coloured food product; Oscar for the best smelling food product; Oscar for the most tasteful food product; Oscar for the healthiest food product; and of course the Raspberry award given to the least appealing food product.</p> <p>After students finish filling in the panel with the sensory analysis of each food product, students have to evaluate objectively the positive and negative aspects of the products on a separate sheet of paper given to six groups. A mixed jury (one student from each team, one teacher and one stakeholder) choose the final awards given to the food products taken into discussion.</p> <p>The activity succeeded in combining serious laboratory aspects related to the sensory food analysis with the pleasure of being in the position to decide on what is the best or worst food product from the Oscar awarding contest. Students felt relaxed during this practical activity, had fun making jokes in the case of some smelling food products. More than this, students enhanced their core competences of observation, dialogue, and facilitation.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Una dintre cele mai apreciate activități din cadrul cursului “Studenti si fermieri impreuna in crearea de noi produse alimentare de la idee pana la punerea lor pe piata” a fost organizarea unei analize senzoriale a mai multor produse alimentare fie aduse de studenti, fie concepute de acestia, urmată de un concurs organizat pe categorii precum: Oscar pentru cei mai colorat produs alimentar, Oscar pentru cel mai mirositor produs alimentar, Oscar pentru cel mai gustos produs alimentar, Oscar pentru cel mai sănătos produs alimentar și, desigur, premiul Raspberry/Zmeurica care a fost acordat celui mai puțin atrăgător produs alimentar.</p> <p>După ce participantii au terminat de completat panelul cu analiza senzorială a fiecărui produs alimentar, au trebuit să evalueze obiectiv aspectele pozitive și negative ale acestor produse pe o foaie separată de hârtie dată celor șase grupuri. Un juriu mixt (un cursant din fiecare echipă, un profesor și un reprezentant al firmelor implicate) a deliberat și a decis cu privire la premiile finale acordate produselor alimentare luate în discuție.</p> <p>Activitatea a reușit să combine activități importante desfășurate în laborator legate de analiza senzorială a alimentelor cu plăcerea</p>

	de a fi în măsură să decidă care este cel mai bun sau cel mai prost produs alimentar din cadrul concursului de decernare a premiilor Oscar. Studentii s-au simțit relaxați în timpul acestei activități practice, s-au distrat făcând glume în cazul unor produse alimentare mirositoare. Mai mult decât atât, au fost îmbunătățite unele competențe de bază importante, cum ar fi observația, dialogul, facilitarea realizată de către elevi/studenti.
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

How to develop competences to facilitate action learning in a multi-stakeholder platform

Nextfood Practice Abstract #44	Partner	College of Dryland Agriculture and Natural Resources, Mekelle University, Ethiopia Mohammed Tilahun, Girmay Tesfay and Zenebe Abraha
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Short title in English	How to develop competences to facilitate action learning in a multi-stakeholder platform
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Learning is an important aspect for a sustainable transition among multi-stakeholder actors in the agrifood system. Following the NEXTFOOD approach, learning can be facilitated through the development of the core competences of Observation, Participation, Dialogue, Reflection and Visioning. In addition to technical skills required for practitioners, these competences will enable continuous learning in the learning arena. If learning continues to occur, practitioners can strive to meet their future wanted situation by continuously learning from the present and past experiences. Learning in a multi-stakeholder platform provides advantages in terms of diversity of views, experiences and local situations. However, it also requires care to meet the diverse needs of the stakeholders. To facilitate better learning and competence development in a multi-stakeholder platform requires:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing manageable group size (<12 members composed of farmers, students, teachers, farmer advisors with gender inclusive team) • Using easy and common language • Exercising all competences together at various platforms (meeting, visit, concrete experiencing) • Assessing the competence development at pre- and post-intervention scales • Using different methods of assessing competencies as appropriate (interview, self-assessment, group reflection sessions)
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Observation as core competence to facilitate action learning at Farmer Training Centres

Nextfood Practice Abstract #45	Partner	College of Dryland Agriculture and Natural Resources, Mekelle University, Ethiopia Mohammed Tilahun, Girmay Tesfay and Zenebe Abraha
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Short title in English	Observation as core competence to facilitate action learning at Farmer Training Centres
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Observation is one of the core competences identified in the NEXTFOOD project important for the transition to a sustainable agrifood system. Observation is a useful competence that paves the way for continuous learning. In the NEXTFOOD Case 3 at the College of Dryland Agriculture and Natural Resources, Mekelle University in Ethiopia, observation helped students to reflect on and be engaged in the real life experiences of farmers. Farmers also learnt from observing the experience of other peer farmers. Observation opened up the opportunity to dialogue, participate and reflect on the real life experiences. Students also appreciated the role of observation in facilitating good visioning and innovation. Observation was the first ranked core competence that helped students to carry out their practice oriented course during the first and second cycle of the action learning sessions in Ethiopia.</p> <p>To effectively learn from observation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan time for observation individually and open the dialogue afterwards • Give time for participants to dialogue within the group or with other people • Encourage group participants to limit their talk during observation • Let participants use easy language for communication • Guide the participants to be divergent (not much influenced by their own bag of knowledge)
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Web-case as experiential part of action learning under the Covid-19 restrictions

Nextfood Practice Abstract #46	Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences, Italy Natalia Rastorgueva, Charlotte Prelorentzos, Paola Migliorini
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Short title in English	Web-case as experiential part of action learning under the Covid-19 restrictions
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Web-case and virtual farm visits have become a necessary part of action-learning under the Covid-19 restrictions at UNISG. These activities were used as an experiential part of action learning during the quarantine and lockdown period to replace real/in presence farm visits. Besides, web-cases, a didactic activity, are used as practice material to further students' analysis and assignments.</p> <p>In the web-case, students read through a long document presentation of the farm case with a photo and transcript of the interviews.</p> <p>In the virtual/online farm visits, students had a videocall with the farmers who gave a short trip in their household and explained principal activities.</p> <p>The organisation of web-cases/virtual visits requires preparation material, a good relation with the stakeholders (farmers), use of electronic tools such as education platforms, high level of organisation in terms of time management, and a good collaboration of all participants (students, teachers and stakeholders).</p> <p>The online farm visits have connected the students and farmers based in different parts of the world and in different time zones. The web-case allowed to overcome distant barriers, to observe agricultural activities, and to organise a dialogue with farmers. Furthermore, web-cases allowed farmers to open their farms to students improving students' observation and dialogue competences.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

NextFood survey on skills for the future of sustainable agrifood / forestry

Nextfood Practice Abstract #47	Partner	Line Friis Lindner, Katherine Flynn (ISEKI-Food Association), Stine Rosenlund Hansen (RUC), Natalia Rastorgueva, Paola Migliorini (UNISG)
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Short title in English	NextFood survey on skills for the future of sustainable agrifood / forestry
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>In the period between summer 2020 and spring 2021, NextFood partners UNISG, RUC and ISEKI-Food Association have been running a survey on skills for the future of sustainable agrifood / forestry. Targeted at farmers, academia, students, food processors and retailers, policy makers, activists in the agrifood and forestry sector, stakeholders are asked in their own words to identify the 3 most important skills or expertise in their daily work and the 3 skills or expertise they would most like to have for their future as a successful stakeholder in sustainable food and forestry.</p> <p>Questions oriented at farmers, advisers to farmers and agriculture students aim to discover the most important skills or expertise missing in the current training and to discover which skills and knowledge this target group would like to learn online and how they would like to learn this.</p> <p>Following, the survey aims to discover the extent to which respondents on a continuum of 1-6 points on a Likert scale agree if a set of skills will become important in the future. The set of skills range from networking skills; communication including about sustainable food and forestry; interdisciplinary skills; collaboration between academics and non-academics ; planning for the future (visioning); efficiency at daily tasks through the use of digitalization, robotics, and other technologies; ability to adapt to changes; skills to use resources efficiently; real-life complex problem-solving; thinking about entire systems and applying holistic knowledge; and skills to shorten/localize the food / forest value chain. The survey was completed by 500 respondents from 40 countries, mainly researchers with a good gender balance, and the results will be published during summer 2021.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Photo Novella Participatory Research for Core Competence Development

Nextfood Practice Abstract #48	Partner American Farm School, Greece Papadopoulou Elisavet and Zafeiriou Georgia
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Short title in English	Photo Novella Participatory Research for Core Competence Development
Short title in native language	Η συμμετοχική έρευνα Photo Novella για την ανάπτυξη των κυρίων δεξιοτήτων
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>During the 3rd cycle of activities and during the online classes of the Covid-19 pandemic, we turned to alternative action-learning methodologies for the enhancement of the NextFood core competences.</p> <p>The Photo Novella participatory research methodology consists of having groups create a photographic gallery based on a given subject. Groups of students chose subjects based on sustainable diets and dedicated a time period to complete their gallery, a project reflection log and a presentation to their peers.</p> <p>This methodology was chosen because it is a creative and experiential way of creating affective representations of reality and analysis of visual narratives. This exercise was designed to enhance all the core competences and the reflection documents from this activity produced a very rich variety of responses:</p> <p>On urban farming:</p> <p>“The image of a bird sitting on a tree branch helped me understand that we could find anything we wanted, anywhere. (...) for a bird or animal it is not strange to find food in an urban environment. On the contrary, we humans find it very strange to see a crop in the city and this might be something that we need to change” (student)</p> <p>and</p> <p>“The photographs of my project are quite realistic and so my feelings are mostly admiration, satisfaction, fantasy and optimism when I think of how my city could look like if we used the available land for farming” (student)</p> <p>On genetically modified foods:</p> <p>“This image might be frightening but at the same time it makes us think and it creates a sort of curiosity regarding the genetic modification of foods” (student)</p> <p>The exercise was also successful at initiating active conversations with students’ peers when asked to present their galleries.</p>

Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes

Κατά τη διάρκεια του 3^{ου} κύκλου δραστηριοτήτων, τα μαθήματα έγιναν εξολοκλήρου διαδικτυακά και η εφαρμογή βιωματικής διδασκαλίας με τα πρότυπα του NEXTFOOD παρουσίαζε πρόκληση.

Γι' αυτό, επιλέξαμε τη μέθοδο Photo Novella. Πρόκειται για μια μεθοδολογία συμμετοχικής έρευνας, όπου ομάδες φοιτητών, επέλεξαν ανάμεσα σε θέματα βιώσιμης διατροφής και κλήθηκαν να δημιουργήσουν μια ομαδική έκθεση φωτογραφίας και να παρουσιάσουν την έκθεσή τους στο μάθημα. Επίσης, κλήθηκαν να συμπληρώσουν ένα προσωπικό ημερολόγιο αντανάκλασης.

Η μέθοδος αυτή αποτελεί έναν δημιουργικό και βιωματικό τρόπο να νοηματοδοτήσουν, να αναλύσουν και να αναπαραστήσουν την πραγματικότητα με οπτικό τρόπο. Έτσι ενισχύσαμε το σύνολο των βασικών δεξιοτήτων και να αποσπάσαμε πολύ πλούσιες απαντήσεις στα ημερολόγια ανατροφοδότησης.

Σχετικά με τις αστικές καλλιέργειες:

«Η εικόνα του πουλιού στο δέντρο με έκανε να σκεφτώ ότι μπορούμε να βρούμε ότι θέλουμε, όπουδήποτε. (...)για τα πουλιά και τα ζώα δεν είναι παράξενο να βρίσκουν τροφή στο αστικό περιβάλλον. Για μας τους ανθρώπους είναι πολύ παράξενο να βλέπουμε καλλιέργειες την πόλη κι αυτό μπορεί να είναι κάτι που πρέπει να αλλάξουμε.» (PNDR)19:2

Και

«Οι φωτογραφίες μου ήταν πολύ ρεαλιστικές και τα συναισθήματα μου ήταν κυρίως θαυμασμού, ικανοποίησης, φαντασίας και αισιοδοξίας όταν σκέφτομαι πώς θα έμοιαζε η πόλη μου αν χρησιμοποιούσαμε την διαθέσιμη γη για καλλιέργειες.» PNDR 26:1

Σχετικά με τα γενετικά τροποποιημένα τρόφιμα:

«Η εικόνα αυτή μπορεί να είναι τρομακτική αλλά ταυτόχρονα μας κάνει να σκεφτόμαστε και δημιουργεί ένα είδος περιέργειας σχετικά με τα γενετικά τροποποιημένα τρόφιμα.» PNDR 20:2

Η μέθοδος του Photo Novella επίσης στάθηκε αφορμή για δυναμικές συζητήσεις κατά τη διάρκεια των παρουσιάσεων.

Link

[Abstracts - NextFood \(nextfood-project.eu\)](https://nextfood-project.eu/abstracts)

Transforming physical meetings into digital – lessons learned

Nextfood Practice Abstract #49	Partner Skogforsk, Sweden Malin Juter and Lotta Woxblom
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Short title in English	Transforming physical meetings into digital – lessons learned
Short title in native language	När fysiska möten omvandlas till digitala – några lärdomar
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Skogforsk is running a vocational course for forestry professionals aiming at a higher understanding about logging techniques and methods to increase quality and number of micro-habitats in production forests.</p> <p>Our main learning source is dialogue around actual situations in everyday work of forest machine operators. The original plan was to arrange meetings in the forest, the home arena of our learners, however, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, most of the planned physical meetings were replaced by online meetings, operators remained in their machines, facilitators in a nearby forest close to the machine team, and researchers remained in their office or in a forest close to their home but distant from the learners.</p> <p>Quite soon we noticed that it was difficult to have a good dialogue at online meetings. How do you get to know someone behind a screen? How do you small talk without coffee breaks? How do you get everyone to talk when you can't feel the atmosphere? In addition, we experienced that the connection swayed and computer batteries ran out during online meetings. To foster dialogue between meetings, we used an app on our phones, however, motivation quickly declined, and activity was low unless facilitators or researchers took initiative and posted photos or questions in the app.</p> <p>Based on our experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital meetings should be pre-scheduled, short, and frequent. • Time for small talk to create commitment and trust in the group is important. • Break-out rooms for dialogue and reflection gets everyone talking and sum up in whole-group meetings. • Important to clarify benefits of the case before starting when working with professional learners. • If you use an app, make someone in charge of moderating who can afford to spend the time.
Short summary for practitioners in native	Skogforsk driver en kurs för yrkesverksamma i skogsbruket. Kursen syftar till att skapa kunskap om och förståelse för tekniker

language on the final or expected outcomes

och metoder vid avverkning för att öka antalet mikrohabitat och kvaliteten på dessa i produktionsskogar. Vår huvudsakliga källa till lärande är dialog kring faktiska situationer i det dagliga arbetet. Den ursprungliga planen var att ordna möten i skogen, det vill säga på våra elevers hemmaarena. På grund av Covid-19 ersattes alla utom ett, av de planerade fysiska mötena med digitala möten med maskinförarna i sina maskiner, kursledaren i en skog nära maskinteamet och forskarna på ett kontor eller i en skog i närheten av hemmet. Vi märkte ganska tidigt att det var svårt att ha en bra dialog med alla deltagare vid digitala möten. Hur lär du känna någon bakom en skärm? Hur får du kontakt när det inte finns möjlighet till småprat över en kopp kaffe? Hur gör du för att inkludera alla i samtalet när du inte kan känna av atmosfären? Det blev inte lättare av det faktum att uppkopplingar svajade och batterier tog slut. För att hålla igång dialogen mellan möten, använde vi en APP på våra telefoner. Motivationen minskade dock snabbt och aktiviteten var låg, såvida inte kursledaren eller forskaren tog initiativ och lade upp foton eller frågor i APPEN. Baserat på vår erfarenhet:

- Digitala möten bör vara förutbestämda, korta och frekventa;
- För att skapa engagemang och tillit i gruppen är det viktigt att ge tid för småprat;
- Uppdelning i små-grupper främjar dialog och reflektion och får alla att prata vid något tillfälle.
- Summering av samtalen görs sen i hela gruppen; Det är viktigt att klargöra mål och nytta med träffarna innan start av en kurs för professionella elever;
- Om du använder en APP, utse ansvarig som kan ta sig tid att moderera den.

Link

[Abstracts - NextFood \(nextfood-project.eu\)](https://nextfood-project.eu/abstracts)

Facilitator's Guide to Visioning for Success

Nextfood Practice Abstract #50	Partner	ISEKI-Food Association, Austria Katherine Flynn
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Short title in English	Facilitator's Guide to Visioning for Success
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Visioning is a core competence for learning in e.g., agrifood. To lead visioning, the facilitator needs a script for a desired success and the participants should be in a quiet place able to write. The facilitator leads 2 minutes of relaxation, slowly: "To relax your body and your mind gently rub your hands together, press them against your face and give yourself a little face rub." Then guidance on relaxed breathing. Then: "Bring your focus to your feet, feel your toes, squeeze them and feel them relax. Move your focus to your lower legs." Continue through the body. Then: "Feel a gentle flow of energy relaxing your brain, face, neck, and entire body." Pause. Now the facilitator leads a time travel to the moment of imagined success. In the case of FoodFactory-4-Us: win a competition, at a conference to present, an organizer asks for a summary. The facilitator reads a script of 3 minutes: "Imagine that you can travel into the future." Detail on this until the desired date. "You are in Brussels, invited because you won." Name some local sights. Then: "Now, you enter the conference center." Then more and more detail on the exact circumstance of success. "Imagine the registration desk, the crowd, the person saying, 'Hello I am the head of the Scientific Committee. I recognize you as the competition winner.'" "Please, tell me about your project?" Now the facilitator must allow participants to see and hear themselves as successes in silence of 1 - 2 minutes (not easy). Then participants write the features of their success. This is an inexpensive way to teach, what is for many, a new competence. Visioning success is recognised in the sports world as an important part of training. The facilitator must be prepared via several rehearsals of the script so that the reading is natural.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Student competence development and perceptions of the multi-actor approach in online learning environments

Nextfood Practice Abstract #51	Partner American Farm School, Greece Papadopoulou Elisavet and Zafeiriou Georgia
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Short title in English	Student competence development and perceptions of the multi-actor approach in online learning environments
Short title in native language	Η ανάπτυξη δεξιοτήτων και οι αντιλήψεις των φοιτητών για συμμετοχή επαγγελματιών σε online μαθησιακή περιβάλλοντα.
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>During the COVID-19 pandemic, due to government restrictions, classes at IHU turned 100% online. The questions we faced regarding the multi-actor approach were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will our farmers be able or willing to connect on-line with our classes? • How are we going to organize online classroom time in order to engage fruitfully? • Are virtual visits going to have the same impact in terms of competence development as real time visits? • Will students engage with the farmers online? <p>Starting with the organizational challenges, the outcomes of this endeavor were very positive as it was easier to organize the virtual visits because of the minimal time and budget resources required from all actors. Time and technical management during the class was also efficient.</p> <p>In terms of impact and engagement, the results were relative to the nature of the module. During the Farm Animal Reproduction module, engagement was high and students reported that they benefited highly from the farmer virtual visits but that the experiential and hands-on part was seriously lacking.</p> <p>By contrast, students from the Nutrition & Nutritional Value of Foods module showed lower engagement levels during class but their reflection documents showed higher levels of impact. Most students referred to specific parts of the visits and talked about how it had impacted and transformed their personal views and their learning experience.</p> <p>From this we have concluded that the modules that are highly practical in nature benefit from the multi-actor approach to a limited degree in online environments. Our experience was</p>

	<p>positive in the sense that we can enhance the multi-actor approach further in the future with virtual visits, but, real life visits and hands-on experience cannot be replaced by any means.</p>
<p>Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes</p>	<p>Κατά τη διάρκεια της πανδημίας COVID-19, τα μαθήματα του πανεπιστημίου έγιναν εξολοκλήρου διαδουκτικά.</p> <p>Τα ερωτήματα που δημιουργήθηκαν ήταν τα εξής:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Θα είναι πρόθυμοι ή ικανοί οι επαγγελματίες να συνδεθούν μαζί μας; • Πώς θα οργανώσουμε τον χρόνο του μαθήματος ώστε να επικωνήσουμε αποτελεσματικά; • Θα έχουν οι επισκέψεις το ίδιο αντίκτυπο σε διαδουκτικό περιβάλλον; • Θα εμπλακούν οι φοιτητές με τους επισκέπτες σε αυτό το περιβάλλον; <p>Αρχίζοντας από τα οργανωσιακά θέματα, η εμπειρία μας ήταν πολύ θετική. Ήταν απλούστερο να οργανωθούν οι επισκέψεις αφού ο χρόνος και τα χρήματα που απαιτούνταν δεν αποτελούσαν πρόβλημα. Η τεχνική και χρονική διαχείριση της τάξης ήταν επίσης αποτελεσματικά.</p> <p>Από άποψη εμπλοκής και αντίκτυπου, τα αποτελέσματα εξαρτήθηκαν από τη φύση του μαθήματος. Στο μάθημα της Ζωικής Αναπαραγωγής η συμμετοχή ήταν υψηλή και οι φοιτητές ανέφεραν ότι κέρδισαν σημαντικά από τις επισκέψεις. Ανέφεραν όμως και ότι έλειπε σημαντικά η πρακτική και εμπειρική πλευρά του μαθήματος.</p> <p>Στο μάθημα της Διατροφής & Διατροφικής Αξίας τροφίμων, συμμετείχαν λιγότερο σε συζητήσεις κατά τη διάρκεια του μαθήματος. Παρόλα αυτά, ανέφεραν σημαντική επίδραση από τις επισκέψεις στις καθημερινές τους στάσεις και στην μαθησιακή τους εμπειρία.</p> <p>Από αυτά συμπεραίνουμε ότι τα μαθήματα που είναι από τη φύση τους πολύ πρακτικά, ωφελούνται περιορισμένα από το διαδουκτικό περιβάλλον μάθησης. Η εμπειρία μας ήταν πολύ χρήσιμη στο ότι μας έμαθε πως μπορούμε να εμπλέξουμε επαγγελματίες ακόμα περισσότερο στο μέλλον διαδουκτικά αλλά δεν μπορεί σε καμία περίπτωση να αντικατασταθούν οι ζωντανές επισκέψεις.</p>
<p>Link</p>	<p>Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)</p>

Student-led reflection in online break-out groups

Nextfood Practice Abstract #52	Partner	ISEKI-Food Association, Austria Line Friis Lindner
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Short title in English	Student-led reflection in online break-out groups
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>In the international online student competition FoodFactory-4-Us led by ISEKI-Food Association – students develop in teams of 3-5 students a unique solution to a real-life food industry challenge while actively participating in 6 online action-learning trainings.</p> <p>In one of the online trainings, we practice student-led reflection where 4-5 students from different teams in break-out groups are given the responsibility of reflection using the initial reflection sessions led by the competition facilitators as a model for how the student-led reflection sessions can be run. Before they are assigned to a group, students watch a short informative video about bioeconomy and are asked to find one episode/ 'experience' in the video that makes an impression on them, followed by 5 minutes reflection in silence. In the groups, students agree on who will be the facilitator and who will be the presenter. The other students in the group are participants. The facilitator leads the conversation around the following question: What are the commonalities between our experiences?. The presenter prepares one slide about these commonalities which are shared in plenary in less than 1 minute.</p> <p>The main objective of such student-led reflection sessions is on the one hand for students to practice facilitation skills – listening without thinking of a response, being curious and learning from others – and on the other hand to design the structure of and leading the reflection session.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Commented [GHL1]:

Observing and reflecting on best practice examples of valorising food biodiversity

Nextfood Practice Abstract #53	Partner ISEKI-Food Association Line Friis Lindner
Short title in English	Observing and reflecting on best practice examples of valorising food biodiversity
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>In the 2020/2021 international online student competition FoodFactory-4-Us led by ISEKI-Food Association, students in teams of 3-5 develop a unique project solution to the topic of valorising food biodiversity while actively participating in 6 online action-learning trainings.</p> <p>In one of these online trainings – the Virtual Visit – we practice the NextFood core competences of observation and reflection. In the “Virtual Visit” students are first presented, in video-format, to three cases related to the valorisation of food biodiversity; (1) vegetable protein to reduce meat consumption; (2) Ethiopian farmers living and working in harmony with nature; and (3) improving biodiversity through the cultivation of old fruit trees in Sicily. As facilitators we ask students beforehand to observe the three cases “out there” in an unbiased manner and reflect about what is most interesting to them and how to relate this to their project solutions. In the deeper reflection session following, we ask students to choose an experience from the videos that made an impression on them, to describe this experience in as much detail as possible, and to reflect on why this experience is important to them. In breakout groups, students have 10 minutes to share their individual reflections and to reflect together on the commonalities between their experiences. In this process, students explore themselves, their perspectives, attributes, and experiences helping them to gain insight into others’ experiences.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Three before asking me (3B4ME)

Nextfood Practice Abstract #54	Partner University of Oradea, Romania Timar Adrian
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Short title in English	Three before asking me (3B4ME)
Short title in native language	Trei înainte de a întreba
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>During the Romanian course, the method “Three before asking me” was applied continuously as a strategy supporting students in becoming independent learners looking for answers in different places and in different ways. Students were given a set of strategies from which they had to choose three and use them before asking the teacher for help:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carefully re-read the question; • Refer to your course, notes or any other resources; • Experiment! Just have a go! • Ask a member of your team! • Ask a member of other team! • Ask a stakeholder! • Stop! Think! Reflect! Use your brain • Ask a clarification question (“Does it mean....?”) <p>Students were advised by their teachers to be careful when asking their fellow students because they may not know the correct answers and they are more likely to learn if they try to figure it out themselves. If they simply get the answer from someone, they are not learning ‘why’ or ‘how’.</p> <p>For this reason, the teachers encouraged students also to choose the strategies like Experiment! or Stop! Think! Reflect!</p> <p>However, students selected other strategies than those recommended by the teachers: starting with asking a member of their group, making appeal to the knowledge of the other more experienced colleagues and stakeholders, continuing with asking members of other groups, and finally referring to the course, notes or internet. The motivation for choosing these strategies were that the time was precious and they needed the answers immediately. These stages designed by the students themselves allowed them to attempt to figure out answers for themselves before asking their teacher. This helped them to understand different problems, improve their knowledge and study skills without simply expecting an immediate answer from their teacher.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Metoda Trei înainte de a întreba a fost aplicată continuu, fiind o strategie care sprijină elevii să devină cursanți independenți, căutând răspunsuri în diferite locuri și în moduri diferite. Elevii au primit un set de strategii din care au trebuit să aleagă trei și să le folosească înainte de a cere ajutorul profesorului:</p> <p>Recitiți cu atenție întrebarea; Consultați cursul, notițele sau orice alte resurse; Experimentați! Doar încercați! Întrebați un membru al echipei dvs.!</p>

	<p>Întrebați un membru al altei echipe! Întrebați o parte interesată! Stop! Gândește! Reflectează! Folosește-ți creierul Puneți o întrebare de clarificare („Înseamnă...?”) Elevii au fost sfătuiți să fie atenți atunci când își întrebă colegii, deoarece este posibil ca aceștia să nu știe răspunsurile corecte și sunt mai predispuși să învețe doar dacă încearcă să-și dea seama ei înșiși. Dacă pur și simplu primesc răspunsul de la cineva, nu învață „de ce” sau „cum”.</p> <p>Din acest motiv, profesorii i-au încurajat să aleagă strategii precum Experimentează! sau Stop! Gândește! Reflectează! Cu toate acestea, elevii au selectat alte strategii decât cele recomandate: începând cu întrebarea adresată unui membru al grupului, apelând la cunoștințele celorlalți colegi și a părților interesate, întrebarea adresată membrilor altor grupuri și în cele din urmă, referindu-se la curs, note sau internet. Motivația pentru alegerea acestor strategii a fost că timpul este prețios iar ei au nevoie imediat de răspunsuri.</p> <p>Aceste etape concepute de participanți le-au permis să încerce să găsească răspunsuri pentru ei înșiși înainte de a le adresa profesorului. Acest lucru i-a ajutat să înțeleagă unele probleme și să-și îmbunătățească cunoștințele fără a aștepta un răspuns din partea profesorului.</p>
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

How to motivate farmers to act as stakeholders in courses conducted at University

Nextfood Practice Abstract #55	Partner	University of Kerala, India Manju S. Nair and Anupama Augustine
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Short title in English	How to motivate farmers to act as stakeholders in courses conducted at University
Short title in native language	കേരള യൂണിവേഴ്സിറ്റി, ഇന്ത്യ
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Farmers act as facilitators during the Certificate Course on Agroecology: Action Research and Education conducted at University of Kerala. Students spend at least one week at selected farms and participate in the farming activity along with farmers learning about farming and food systems. The active participation of farmers incited major recommendations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Field visits and university staff dialoguing with the farmer prior to course begin: Visiting the farm and understanding the economic and socio-cultural peculiarities of farmer prior to the course can help arriving at a mutually beneficial agreement with the farmer. At this point, the goal of the course and the expected role of the farmer as facilitator can be clarified. 2. Identifying the scope of intervention at the farm and communicating with the farmer: Being illiterate and hailing from poor background, many farmers face problems such as lack of proper documentation of farm activities, ignorance of procedures relating to various government schemes and support programmes and technical incompetence etc. Developing a joint action plan as part of the curriculum to address these issues can encourage farmers. 3. Joint visioning with the farmer organised by students: Developing a joint vision of the farm regarding how to develop the farm over a period and jolting both short term and long-term plans. 4. Preparation and submission of Client Document: highlighting the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the farm.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>കേരള യൂണിവേഴ്സിറ്റി സംഘടിപ്പിക്കുന്ന അഗ്രോ ഇക്കോളജി കോഴ്സിൽ ഭാഗഭാക്കുകാർ കർഷകരെ എങ്ങനെ പ്രോത്സാഹിപ്പിക്കാം.</p> <p>കേരള യൂണിവേഴ്സിറ്റി നടത്തുന്ന അഗ്രോ ഇക്കോളജി ആക്ഷൻ റിസർച്ച് ആൻഡ് എജ്യൂക്കേഷൻ എന്ന സർട്ടിഫിക്കറ്റ് കോഴ്സിന്റെ സുഗമമായ നടത്തിപ്പിന് വിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾക്കാവശ്യമായ</p>

മാർഗനിർദ്ദേശങ്ങൾ നൽകി കൊണ്ട് കർഷകർ മികച്ച രീതിയിൽ ഇടപെടുന്നു. കോപ്ലിന്റെ ഭാഗമായി കുട്ടികൾ ഒരാഴ്ചക്കാലം തിരഞ്ഞെടുക്കപ്പെട്ട കൃഷി സ്ഥലങ്ങളിൽ കർഷകരോടൊപ്പം ചെലവഴിക്കുകയും അവരോടൊപ്പം കാർഷിക വൃത്തികളിൽ ഏർപ്പെട്ട് കാർഷിക ഭക്ഷ്യ വ്യവസ്ഥകളെക്കുറിച്ച് അറിവുകൾ നേടുകയും ചെയ്യുന്നു. ഈ കോപ്ലിലെ കർഷകരുടെ മികച്ച പങ്കാളിത്തം താഴെപ്പറയുന്ന നിർദ്ദേശങ്ങൾ മുന്നോട്ടു വയ്ക്കാൻ പ്രേരിപ്പിക്കുന്നു.

1. യൂണിവേഴ്സിറ്റി അധികൃതരുടെ നേതൃത്വത്തിൽ കൃഷി സ്ഥലം സന്ദർശിക്കുകയും കർഷകരുമായി ആശയവിനിമയം നടത്തുകയും ചെയ്യുന്നു. കോപ്ലി ആരംഭിക്കുന്നതിന് മുൻപ് യൂണിവേഴ്സിറ്റി അധികൃതരുടെ നേതൃത്വത്തിൽ കൃഷി സ്ഥലം സന്ദർശിക്കുകയും കർഷകരുടെ സാമൂഹിക, സാമ്പത്തിക, സാംസ്കാരിക പരിതസ്ഥിതി മനസ്സിലാക്കുകയും ചെയ്യുന്നതുവഴി ഇരുകൂട്ടർക്കും പ്രയോജനകരമായ ഒരു ഉടമ്പടിയിൽ ഏർപ്പെടാൻ സാധിക്കും. ഇപ്രകാരം ചെയ്യുന്നതിലൂടെ കോപ്ലിന്റെ ലക്ഷ്യവും കർഷകരുടെ പങ്കും കൂടുതൽ വ്യക്തമാക്കപ്പെടുകയും ചെയ്യും.

2. കൃഷി സ്ഥലത്തെ ഇടപെടലുകളുടെ സാധ്യതകൾ തിരിച്ചറിഞ്ഞ് കർഷകരുമായി പങ്കുവയ്ക്കുന്നു. നിരക്ഷരത, സാമ്പത്തികമായ പിന്നോക്ക അവസ്ഥ എന്നിവ കാരണം കർഷകർ നിരവധി പ്രശ്നങ്ങൾ അഭിമുഖീകരിക്കുന്നുണ്ട്. കാർഷിക പ്രവൃത്തികളുടെ കൃത്യമായ രേഖപ്പെടുത്തലിന്റെ അഭാവം, ഗവൺമെന്റിന്റെ വിവിധ പദ്ധതികളുടെ നടപടിക്രമങ്ങളെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള അജ്ഞത, സാങ്കേതികവിദ്യകൾ പ്രയോജനപ്പെടുത്താനുള്ള ബുദ്ധിമുട്ട് എന്നിവ ഉദാഹരണങ്ങളാണ്. ഈ സാഹചര്യത്തിൽ കോപ്ലിന്റെ ഭാഗമായി ഒരു സംയുക്ത കർമ്മ പദ്ധതി ആവിഷ്കരിച്ചുകൊണ്ട് പ്രശ്നങ്ങൾ അഭിമുഖീകരിക്കാൻ കർഷകരെ സഹായിക്കുവാനും കോപ്ലിൽ സജീവമായി പങ്കെടുക്കാൻ പ്രേരിപ്പിക്കാനും സാധിക്കും.

	<p>3.കർഷകരും വിദ്യാർത്ഥികളും സംയുക്തമായി ആലോചിച്ചു കൃഷി സ്ഥല വികസനത്തിനായി ഹ്രസ്വകാല ദീർഘകാല പദ്ധതികൾ രൂപീകരിക്കുന്നു.</p> <p>4.പഠനവിധേയമാക്കിയ കൃഷി സ്ഥലത്തിന്റെ സാധ്യതകൾ, വെല്ലുവിളികൾ, പരിമിതികൾ എന്നിവ തിരിച്ചറിഞ്ഞ് ക്ലയന്റ് ഡോക്യുമെന്റ് തയ്യാറാക്കി സമർപ്പിക്കുന്നു.</p>
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Motivations for farmers to participate in action learning course

Nextfood Practice Abstract #56	Partner	University of Kerala, India Manju S. Nair and Anupama Augustine
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Short title in English	Motivations for farmers to participate in action learning course
Short title in native language	കോഴ്സിൽ പങ്കാളികളാകാൻ കർഷകരെ പ്രോത്സാഹിപ്പിക്കുന്ന ഘടകങ്ങൾ.
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Farmers actively participate in the Certificate Course on Agroecology: Action Research and Education conducted at University of Kerala. Farmers join in the planning workshop prior to the course and act as facilitators in the course by guiding students during field stay. Based on farmers' experience, major recommendations are highlighted:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participation in the course helps to interact with officials, academics and students which is otherwise impossible. It improves self-confidence and status of farmers. 2. Participation in the course is an opportunity to dialogue with students, the upcoming generation relating to traditional agricultural practices and values. 3. From academics and students, scientific techniques can be learned and a synthesis of traditional and modern techniques can be practiced in farms 4. The course provides an opportunity to familiarise with fellow farmers and learn from each other. It also helps to understand the contemporary farming techniques and marketing techniques in nearby farms. 5. Students participate in the farming activity which is a help for farmers. Students help farmers in ploughing, sowing, harvesting and marketing activities based on the curriculum plan. Also, farmers can teach students farming practices. 6. Participation in the course can improve interpersonal skills, since it provides an opportunity to deal with a multitude of stakeholders. 7. Shared visioning and client documents can be used as a scientific draft to develop the farm. The comprehensive report prepared by students with the support of academics including farmers' vision include practical tips to improve farms.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	കേരള യൂണിവേഴ്സിറ്റി നടത്തുന്ന അഗ്രോ ഇക്കോളജി ആക്ഷൻ റിസർച്ച് ആൻഡ് എജ്യൂക്കേഷൻ എന്ന സർട്ടിഫിക്കറ്റ് കോഴ്സിൽ കർഷകരുടെ സജീവമായ പങ്കാളിത്തം ശ്രദ്ധേയമായിരുന്നു. കർഷകർ വർക്ക് ഷോപ്പുകളിൽ പങ്കെടുക്കുകയും

കോഴ്സിന്റെ മുന്നോട്ടുള്ള നടത്തിപ്പിന് സഹായികളായി കൃഷി സ്ഥല സന്ദർശന വിവരശേഖരണ സമയങ്ങളിൽ വിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾക്കാവശ്യമായ മാർഗനിർദ്ദേശങ്ങൾ നൽകുകയും ചെയ്യും. കർഷകരുടെ അനുഭവങ്ങൾ താഴെപ്പറയുന്ന നിർദ്ദേശങ്ങൾ അടിവരയിടുന്നു.

1. കോഴ്സിലെ പങ്കാളിത്തം കർഷകരെ അക്കാദമിക വിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾ, ഉദ്യോഗസ്ഥർ, വിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾ എന്നിവരുമായി ആശയവിനിമയം നടത്തുന്നതിന് സഹായിക്കുന്നു. ഇത് കർഷകരുടെ ആത്മവിശ്വാസവും, സാമൂഹിക നിലവാരവും മെച്ചപ്പെടാൻ സഹായകമാകുന്നു.

2. പരമ്പരാഗത കാർഷിക പ്രവൃത്തികളെയും, മൂല്യങ്ങളേയും കുറിച്ച് വളർന്നു വരുന്ന തലമുറയോട് സംവദിക്കാൻ കർഷകർക്ക് അവസരം ലഭിക്കുന്നു.

3. അക്കാദമികവിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾ, വിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾ എന്നിവരിൽ നിന്നും പുതിയ ശാസ്ത്ര സാങ്കേതിക വിദ്യകളെക്കുറിച്ച് മനസ്സിലാക്കുവാനും അത് കാർഷികവൃത്തികളിൽ പ്രയോജനപ്പെടുത്തുവാനും കർഷകർക്ക് സാധിക്കുന്നു.

4. മറ്റ് കർഷകരെ പരിചയപ്പെടുവാനും പരസ്പരം അറിവുകൾ പങ്കുവയ്ക്കുവാനും ഈ കോഴ്സ് കർഷകർക്ക് അവസരം നൽകുന്നു. അതോടൊപ്പം സമകാലിക കൃഷിരീതികൾ, വിപണനതന്ത്രങ്ങൾ, എന്നിവയെക്കുറിച്ച് മനസ്സിലാക്കാൻ കർഷകർക്ക്, സാഹചര്യമൊരുക്കുകയും ചെയ്യുന്നു.

5. കാർഷികവൃത്തികളിൽ കർഷകരോടൊപ്പം വിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾ പങ്കെടുക്കുന്നത് കർഷകന് സഹായകമാകും. കർഷകർക്ക് വിദ്യാർത്ഥികളെ കൃഷിരീതികളെപ്പറ്റി പഠിപ്പിക്കാനും സാധിക്കും.

6. കോഴ്സിന്റെ ഭാഗമായി വിവിധ മേഖലകളെ പ്രതിനിധീകരിക്കുന്നവരുമായി ആശയവിനിമയം നടത്താനുള്ള അവസരങ്ങൾ സൃഷ്ടിക്കപ്പെടുന്നതുവഴി കർഷകർക്ക്

	<p>വ്യക്തികളുമായി മികച്ച രീതിയിൽ ഇടപെടാൻ സഹായകമായ നൈപുണികൾ മെച്ചപ്പെടുത്തുവാൻ സാധിക്കുന്നു.</p> <p>7. വിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾ അക്കാദമിക വിദ്യാഭ്യാസ സഹായത്തോടെ തയ്യാറാക്കുന്ന സമഗ്രമായ റിപ്പോർട്ട് കൃഷിസ്ഥല വികസനത്തിനുള്ള പ്രായോഗിക നിർദ്ദേശങ്ങൾ ഉൾക്കൊള്ളുന്നു. ക്ലബ്ബ് ഡോക്യുമെന്റ്, കൃഷിസ്ഥലത്തെക്കുറിച്ച് വിദ്യാർത്ഥികൾ വികസിപ്പിക്കുന്ന ഭാവനാ പരമായ ഉൾക്കാഴ്ചകൾ എന്നിവ കൃഷിസ്ഥല വികസനത്തിനു സഹായിക്കുന്ന ശാസ്ത്രീയ രേഖകളായി ഉപയോഗപ്പെടുത്താം.</p>
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Nextfood Audit Tool – self-assessment and reflection

Nextfood Practice Abstract #57	Partner	[Stine Rosenlund Hansen, Ivanche Dimitrievski, Parthib Basu] [Author 1: Roskilde University, Author 2: Lund University, Author 3: University of Calcutta]
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Short title in English	Nextfood Audit Tool – self-assessment and reflection
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Agri-food and forestry sectors develop rapidly, while facing complex challenges such as globalization and climate change. Educational actors must adapt to facilitate the development of the skills and competences that students need to operate as professionals in these sectors in the future.</p> <p>For this purpose, NextFood has developed the NextFood Audit Tool, which is designed to generate awareness and reflection among educational actors.</p> <p>The Audit Tool consists of three interconnected parts: In the first part, users provide background information on professional roles, gender, age, work experience, and type of education. This will enable perspectival analyses of the results and comparisons. The second part is a self-assessment tool, where users will rank how their programme, course, or other educational activity perform in relation to achieving the needed skills and competences. The third part introduces reflection exercises, designed to engage educators in reflection on various ways to develop their educational activities further.</p> <p>The Audit tool provides educational actors insights regarding their capacities to contribute towards developing a next generation of agri-food and forestry professionals, by ensuring that education and training systems are fit for purpose and continuously updated.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Action research as a didactic activity for improving the competence of reflection

Nextfood Practice Abstract #58	Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences, Italy Natalia Rastorgueva, Charlotte Prelorenzoz, Paola Migliorini
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Short title in English	Action research as a didactic activity for improving the competence of reflection
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Action research was developed as a main and continuous didactic activity for the new Master in Agroecology and Food Sovereignty (University of Gastronomic Sciences, Pollenzo, Italy) Thus, all theoretical and experiential phases of the Master include action research. However, the practical application of action research under the Covid-19 restrictions has become a challenge in general.</p> <p>Action research includes development of the core competences. In order to implement the core competences, we encouraged students to shift from classical written exam to reflection-based written assignment. This assignment includes a student's portfolio, which is a combination of academic work and other forms of educational evidence assembled for the purpose of (1) evaluating coursework quality, learning progress, and academic achievement; (2) determining whether students have met learning standards or other academic requirements for courses, grade-level promotion, and graduation; (3) helping students reflect on their academic goals and progress as learners; and (4) creating a lasting archive of academic work products, accomplishments, and other documentation.</p> <p>Besides, every week students prepared an individual reflection journals in which they gave feedback on didactic activities (classes, physical and online farm visits, garden activities, group work) thereby connecting received theoretical and practical activities with their inner world. Action research encourages students to significantly improve their reflection competence.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Strategies for improvements of the educational system through meeting with stakeholders

Nextfood Practice Abstract #59	Partner	University of Bologna, Italy Davide Viaggi, Yaprak Kurtsal, Giacomo Rinaldi, Federica Savini
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Short title in English	Strategies for improvements of the educational system through meeting with stakeholders
Short title in native language	Strategie per migliorare il sistema educativo attraverso l'incontro con gli stakeholders
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>In NEXTFOOD, strategies have been identified for improving the educational and training system in the Agriculture, Food and Forestry (AFF) sectors through a round of 10 workshops in different regions of the world with the participation of more than 60 stakeholders (academics, advisors and officers from a variety of public and private organizations). Despite the different origins and contexts, stakeholders shared the same vision for many aspects of a new educational agenda in AFF sectors. On some points, diverging opinions reflected the different backgrounds of each workshop and each participant.</p> <p>The most relevant strategies identified were: i) increasing practical knowledge and experiences; ii) improving skills and competences, mostly in the field of digital skills; iii) enhancing collaborations among different actors involved in the educational process (schools, professional institutes, universities, research institutes, ministries, advisors, etc.); iv) setting up a dialogue with stakeholders external to academy.</p> <p>Furthermore, widespread opinions were both the importance of attracting new targets (e.g. young urban people) and making the sector gender neutral (breaking down barriers for females).</p> <p>Various indications also pointed directly to suggested areas of improvement of existing policies, such as: a) reduction of administrative burden to allow a more flexible construction of educational and training processes; b) sharing of a common accreditation system across the EU to enhance international mobility and networking; c) filling the digital gap with financial and technical support; d) facilitating social inclusion to young people and women in education processes leading to better employment opportunities.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Il progetto NEXTFOOD ha identificato strategie per il miglioramento del sistema formativo nell'agroalimentare e nel settore forestale (settori AFF) attraverso 10 workshop in diverse regioni del mondo e con la partecipazione di più di 60 stakeholder invitati (accademici, ricercatori, consulenti e funzionari di organizzazioni sia pubbliche che private). Nonostante la diversità di origine e contesti, i partecipanti condividevano per molti aspetti la stessa visione di</p>

	<p>una futura agenda formativa nei settori AFF. Su alcuni punti, opinioni diverse hanno rispecchiato le peculiarità di ogni workshop e ogni partecipante.</p> <p>Le più rilevanti strategie individuate sono state: i) incrementare il sapere pratico e le esperienze sul campo; ii) aumentare le competenze, soprattutto quelle digitali; iii) aumentare le collaborazioni tra gli attori coinvolti nella formazione (scuole, istituti professionali, università, ministeri, consulenti, ecc.); iv) impostare un dialogo con attori esterni al mondo formativo (industria, comunità locali, paesi esteri, ecc.).</p> <p>Inoltre, opinioni diffuse sono l'importanza di attrarre nuovi soggetti (es. i giovani da aree urbane) e la neutralità di genere nel settore (abbattendo le barriere per le donne).</p> <p>Varie indicazioni hanno poi suggerito aree di miglioramento delle politiche esistenti, come: a) ridurre la pressione amministrativa per una più flessibile costruzione dei processi educativi; b) condividere un sistema di accreditamento comune tra gli Stati UE, per potenziare la mobilità internazionale e il fare rete; c) colmare le lacune digitali con supporto tecnico e finanziario; d) facilitare l'inclusione sociale di giovani e donne nei processi educativi al fine di migliorare le opportunità lavorative.</p>
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Reflection as a core competence in the NextFood approach

Nextfood Practice Abstract #60	Partner NMBU, Norway Marie Henriksen Bogstad
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Short title in English	Reflection as a core competence in the NextFood approach
Short title in native language	Refleksjon som en nøkkelkompetanse i NextFood-modellen
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Reflection is a structured activity for making sense of the multitude of experiences that students, farmers and other stakeholders have in the agrifood- and forestry system. Reflection is essential to bridge the gap between past, present and future linking immediate experiences, thoughts and feelings to existing knowledge and plans for further development as professionals. Being able to reflect entails an examination of the world 'out there' – the farming and food systems – and the world 'in here', seeing experiences in the light of attitudes, actions and interactions. As a competence, reflection needs to be trained as a structured activity for learning, developing the ability to link insights, experience and theory, while at the same time identifying room for further exploration and work. Hence, reflection is at the heart of understanding and developing sustainable farm, food and forestry systems.</p> <p>When training reflection in an action learning environment, metaphorically the learner can be seen as the ruminant and the learning experience as the grass on which it chews. In cultivating reflection, it is important to introduce reflection as a concept, organize reflection sessions frequently (individually and in groups), write a reflection diary, and provide tools for reflection. Ask your learners to reflect on: What did I observe/experience? What did I feel/think/learn about this? What are the questions I am asking myself? What will I do to find the answers? What are the implications for my own development? And ask yourself as a teacher, after completing a session: How did I experience this session/course? How do I think my students experienced this session/course? If I were to conduct the same session/course again, what would I do differently?</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Refleksjon er en aktivitet strukturert for å gi mening til de mangfoldige opplevelsene studenter, bønder og andre aktører har i gårds-, skogs- og matsystemer. Gjennom refleksjon knytter en sine umiddelbare opplevelser, tanker og følelser til eksisterende kunnskap (litteratur), samt planer for fremtidig utvikling som profesjonelle. Å ha evnen til å reflektere innebærer å undersøke verden <i>der ute</i> – i mat- og landbrukssystemer – og verden <i>her inne</i>, i lys av holdninger og handlinger. Som en kompetanse må refleksjon øves på organisert vis, og introduseres som en strukturert aktivitet som krever fokus og intensjon. På den måten utvikler man evnen til å knytte innsikt med opplevelser og teori – samtidig som man identifiserer handlingsrom for fremtidig</p>

	<p>arbeid. Altså er refleksjon essensielt for å forstå og utvikle bærekraftige, gårds-, mat- og skogsystemer. Refleksjon i en aksjonslæringssetting kan sammenlignes med det med å tygge drøv. Den som lærer er drøvtyggeren og læringsaktiviteten er graset. Når man jobber med refleksjon på denne måten er det viktig å introdusere konseptet tidlig, samt å organisere jevnlige refleksjonssesjoner individuelt og gruppevis. Det kan også være fint å skrive en refleksjonsdagbok. Lag gjerne noen refleksjonsspørsmål . For eksempel:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hva observert/opplevde jeg? - Hva følte/tenkte/lærte jeg om dette? - Hvilke spørsmål stiller jeg meg nå? - Hva skal jeg gjøre for å besvare disse? - Hvilke implikasjoner har dette for min egen utvikling? <p>Som lærer, kan du stille deg selv disse spørsmålene etter en endt time/kurs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hvordan opplevde jeg denne timen/kurset? - Hvordan tror jeg studentene mine opplevde det? <p>Hvis jeg skulle gjort det igjen, hva ville jeg gjort annerledes?</p>
Link	Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)

Visionary thinking as a core competence in the NextFood approach

Nextfood Practice Abstract #61	Partner	NMBU, Norway Marie Henriksen Bogstad
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Short title in English	Visionary thinking as a core competence in the NextFood approach
Short title in native language	Visjonstenkning som nøkkelkompetanse i NextFood-modellen
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>In the NextFood educational approach, visionary thinking is a competence whereby the learners imagine a desired future within specific agrifood and forestry systems. Students practice visionary thinking together with farmers and other stakeholders in the field. Such a shared activity can bring people of different backgrounds, values and assumptions together and open up for co-creation of future oriented knowledge. When a shared vision is created, the room for transformative change increases as the vision provides direction for action plans and decisions along the way. Having a shared vision based on what is meaningful for a group collectively also creates ownership and individual responsibility.</p> <p>Visionary thinking is a holistic and pro-active approach to the future, different from problem solving which puts the problem at the centre of attention. Visionary thinking encourages sole focus on thinking about the desired future focussing not on what stakeholders want to get away from, but rather what they want to create. Visionary thinking can be developed only through practice and when training visionary thinking, keep in mind that it is a very versatile approach that can be utilized in many ways, scales and situations. Before starting a visioning exercise 1) create the right environment and thoroughly inform participants about the process; 2) ask questions that allow for the imagination to 'run free'. In many cases the use of guided imagery to 'travel to the future', can serve as a fruitful way to observe and visualize what the desired future state is all about. In any case, it is important to create a relaxing atmosphere that allows for suspension of judgement.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>I NextFood-modellen er visjonstenking en kompetanse hvor man forestiller seg en ønsket fremtid innenfor et spesifikt mat-, gårds- eller skogssystem. Studenter praktiserer visjonstenking med bønder og andre aktører ute i felten. En slik kollektiv aktivitet kan bidra til å forene ulike interesser, aktiviteter og verdier, og åpne opp for samskaping av fremtidsrettet kunnskap. Når en delt visjon er utformet øker rommet for transformativ endring da visjonen fungerer som et nav for handlingsplaner og avgjørelser underveis. Å ha en delt visjon basert på hva som er viktig for en gruppe i fellesskap øker også eierskap og individuelt ansvar.</p>

	<p>Visjonstenking er en helhetlig og proaktiv tilnærming til fremtiden, forskjellig fra problemløsning som er reaktiv og spesifikk. Problemløsning setter problemet i forsetet, mens visjonstenking heller vier fullt fokus til forestillingen om den ønskede fremtiden. Oppmerksomheten er da rettet mot hva aktørene ønsker skape.</p> <p>Som for en hvilken som helst kompetanse kan evnen til å utøve visjonstenking kun utvikles gjennom praksis. Når man øver på visjonstenking er det viktig å huske at det er en allsidig tilnærming som kan brukes på mange ulike måter og situasjoner. Før du starter en øvelse i visjonstenking er det viktig å sørge for trygge omgivelser og informere godt om prosessen i forkant. Det er også viktig å stille spørsmål som oppmuntrer til frislipp av fantasien. I mange situasjoner kan det fungere å bruke en 'guidet forestilling' som en metode for å reise frem i tid, og for å observere og visualisere hva den ønskede fremtiden handler om. Uansett er det viktig å skape en avslappet atmosfære som tillater deltakerne å se bort ifra fordommer.</p>
<p>Link</p>	<p>Abstracts - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)</p>